

A very rare mononuclear nickel(II) species bonded via oxygen atom of oximato function using pyridylazo-oxime type of ligands

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The oxime function in conjunction with other donors have been found to stabilize pseudo-octahedral nickel complexes, especially over the valence state 2–4^{1–4}. The notable examples of such ligands include the dioximes^{1,5}, imine-oximes³, ketoximes⁷ and the azo-oximes⁸. In the present work, we explore a new situation where the azo-oxime function is in conjunction with a pyridyl group as in HL, **1**. The chemistry of HL with manganese and iron has already been investigated and reported elsewhere⁹ but the nickel chemistry has not been developed.

We report here the synthesis and characterization of bis-chelates of the type $[\text{NiL}_2]\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$, **2**, using the tridentate pyridylazo-oxime ligand, **1**. The gross structure of the complexes are predicted from EPR measurements by doping $[\text{MnL}_2]\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ ⁹ into $[\text{NiL}_2]\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ lattice. It involves the very rare⁹ regio-specific mononuclear binding of oximato function via oxygen as in **2**. In mononuclear oximato complexes the metal ions are known to bind via nitrogen site only and to the best of our knowledge these are one of the rare examples of mononuclear nickel(II) complexes bonded via oxygen atom of oximato function.

Results and Discussion

The ligand system HL (H refers to the dissociable oxime

proton) is a blend of azopyridine¹⁰ and azooxime^{1,4,8,9} as highlighted by the binding modes **3** and **4**, respectively. The reaction of nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate with HL in methanol furnished reddish brown $[\text{NiL}_2]$ in excellent yields. The complexes were crystallized from dichloromethane-hexane

and isolated as dichloromethane adducts, $[\text{NiL}_2]\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$. They are paramagnetic for two unpaired electrons, which is indicative of their pseudo-octahedral d^8 configuration ($S=1$) and in solution they exhibit a broad band around 500 nm (Table 1). The complexes show characteristic N=N and N–O stretches¹¹ at ~ 1330 and 1250 cm^{-1} , respectively. They are electroactive and display two cyclic voltammetric responses in acetonitrile solution (Table 1, Fig. 1). The couples near 0.7 and -0.6 V are respectively assigned to metal oxidation and azo reduction¹², but the processes are far from being reversible.

Table 1. Spectral, electrochemical^a and magnetic data of $[\text{NiL}_2]\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$

Compd.	λ_{max} , nm ^b	$E_{1/2}$ ^c	μ_{eff} ^e , μ_B
Yield (%), Colour	ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$	$(\Delta E_p)^d$, mV	
$[\text{NiL}_2]\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ (90)	490 (8100)	0.70 (290), -0.59 (330)	2.98
$[\text{NiL}_2]\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ (88)	500 (7830)	0.66 (280), -0.54 (310)	3.07

^aIn acetonitrile at a platinum disk electrode; supporting electrolyte tetraethylammonium perchlorate (TEAP, 0.1 M); scan rate, 50 mV s^{-1} , reference electrode SCE; solute concentration, $\sim 10^{-3}\text{ M}$. ^bIn dichloromethane. ^c $E_{1/2}$ is calculated as the average of anodic (E_{pa}) and cathodic (E_{pc}) peak potentials. ^d $\Delta E_p = E_{\text{pa}} - E_{\text{pc}}$. ^eIn polycrystalline state at 298 K.

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Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram (scan rate, 50 mV s^{-1}) of an $\sim 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ solution of $[\text{NiL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ in acetonitrile (0.1 M TEAP) at a platinum electrode.

The $[\text{NiL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ complexes are EPR-silent, evidently due to rapid relaxation and can freely form solid solutions with $[\text{MnL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ which have exclusively meridional geometry⁹. The EPR spectra of the doped lattice is axial with $g_{\parallel} \sim 1.97$ and $g_{\perp} \sim 2.02$ (Table 2, Fig. 2). The EPR spectra of $[\text{MnL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ in frozen (77 K) dichloromethane-toluene (1 : 1) glass are closely similar to that in $[\text{NiL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ lattice (Fig. 2). This proves that $[\text{NiL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ has the same gross geometry (motif 2) as $[\text{MnL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$. In principle, $[\text{NiL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ should have rhombic symmetry but in practice the rhombic component of the ligand field is not resolved and hence the EPR spectra is axial.

Table 2. EPR parameters^a of the doped complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{Mn})\text{L}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$

Compd.	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{\parallel}, G	A_{\perp}, G
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Mn})\text{L}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$	1.965	2.028	170	60
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Mn})\text{L}_2^1].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$	1.971	2.023	165	64

^aIn polycrystalline state.

The unusual behavior of the oximato function, viz. bonding to nickel(II) via oxygen atom in mononuclear complexes, is controlled by the presence of pyridyl function which imposes the five-membered 2-azopyridine chelation mode, 3. In order to involve in tridentate bicyclic chelation, the oximato-N of HL may involve in bonding, forming a four-membered ring or the oximato-O, to form a five-membered ring juxtaposed with azopyridine ring. The second one being more stable, is observed in practice.

Conclusion: The pyridylazo-oxime ligand system, HL, behaves as a tridentate monoanionic donor towards bivalent nickel to form bis-chelate of the type $[\text{NiL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$. The complexes are pseudooctahedral d^8 systems and are

Fig. 2. X-Band EPR spectra of $[\text{NiL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ doped into $[\text{MnL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ (-) in polycrystalline form at 298 K and $[\text{MnL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ in dichloromethane-toluene (1 : 1) glass at 77 K (---); DPPH = diphenylpicrylhydrazyl.

redox-active with respect to metal oxidation and azo reduction. Their isomorphism with the reported $[\text{MnL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ complexes has been established from doped EPR measurements in polycrystalline state, revealing the very rare mononuclear binding of the oximato function via the oxygen atom to bivalent nickel.

Experimental

A Hitachi 330 spectrophotometer was used to record UV-Vis spectra. EPR spectra were recorded in the X-band on a Varian E-109 spectrometer fitted with a quartz dewar. The spectra were calibrated with respect to DPPH ($g = 2.0037$). Magnetic susceptibilities were measured with a PAR 155 vibrating sample magnetometer fitted with a Walker Scientific L75BAL magnet. A Perkin-Elmer 2400 Series (II) elemental analyzer was used to collect microanalytical data (CHN). Electrochemical measurements were performed under nitrogen atmosphere on a PAR 370-4 electrochemistry system using solvents and supporting electrolytes purified/prepared as before¹³. All potentials are referenced to the saturated calomel electrode (SCE). IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer.

The ligands and $[\text{MnL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ complexes were synthesized by reported methods⁹, while the nickel(II) complexes by a general method. Details of a representative case is given below. Solvents and reagents were used as obtained from commercial sources.

Dichloromethane adduct of bis[2-pyridylazo]-1-benzaldoximato]nickel(II), $[\text{NiL}_2].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$: The complex was prepared by adding a methanolic solution (10 ml) of HL¹ (90 mg, 0.4 mmol) to a solution containing $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (50 mg, 0.2 mmol) and the dark red-

dish brown solution so formed was stirred magnetically for 2 h. The deposited dark-brown crystalline solid was filtered off, washed several times with 1 : 1 aqueous methanol, dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl₂ and recrystallized from dichloromethane-hexane, (92 mg, 90%); (Found : C, 50.64; H, 3.38; N, 18.82. C₂₅H₂₀N₈O₂Cl₂Ni requires : C, 50.54; H, 3.39; N, 18.86%). The [NiL₂].CH₂Cl₂ complex was prepared by following similar procedures : (Found : C, 52.07; H, 3.34; N, 18.09. C₂₇H₂₄N₈O₂Cl₂Ni requires : C, 52.12; H, 3.86; N, 18.02%).

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